

European Nucleotide Archive

Webin-CLI Read Data Submission

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Contents

- ENA Background
- Why submit data to the ENA?
- Data Structure at the ENA
 - ENA Data Model
 - ENA Metadata Model
- Data submission at the ENA
 - Webin-CLI Data Submission
- Summary
- Workshop - read data submission with Webin-CLI

ENA Background: What is ENA?

Open platform for the management, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data

- **Globally comprehensive scientific record** and European node of **INSDC**
- **Broad scope** covering raw data, through layers of interpretation and context
- **Connectivity** with broader EMBL-EBI resources
- Sequence data **foundation**
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training
- **Management**, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals

Archive

Platform

Submitting data to the ENA

Why is it important to share data?

- Findability
- Accessibility
- Reproducibility/Reusability
- Interoperability
- Community collaboration
- Data standards

Maximum value

Submitting data to the ENA

All data in the ENA is submitted by members of the research community

What motivates people to submit?

- Open data
- Reproducibility
- Reusability
- 3rd party access
- Archival
- **Publication**
- Downstream analyses

*The data lifecycle, from ELIXIR Europe
<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>*

Data resources at EMBL-EBI

ENA - an ELIXIR Core Data Resource

- The ENA is part of the wider ecosystem of biodata resources
- Recognised as an ELIXIR CDR and Global Core Biodata Resource by the Global Biodata Coalition
- Integration into a system of biodata resources increases value in genomics data

GLOBAL
CORE
BIODATA
RESOURCE

Data Structure at ENA

ENA Data Structure

- ENA stores huge amounts of data
 - ... from many users
 - ... with samples from many taxa
 - ... who use many different techniques
 - ... and sequence on many different platforms
- But we need to display data in a consistent manner
- A robust model is the first step in achieving this

ENA Data model

Sequence data is organised into tiers:

- **Reads:** raw sequence data
- **Assemblies:** reconstructions of actual replicons
- **Annotations:** interpretations of biological function

Annotation and **assembly** are frequently paired

ENA Metadata Model

- Data without any context has no value
- Metadata tells us how sequence data was produced
- Makes it possible to compare datasets:
*“I want to see metagenome data from insect gut ..
... collected from Japan ...
... sampled between 2021 and 2023 ...
... compared with the same from the United Kingdom”*

- Archives have spent a lot of time thinking about this!

ENA Metadata Model: Study

- Rearing systems play an important role in animal welfare, health and the composition of the gut microbiome.
- Shi et al. wanted to study differences in caecal microbiome of hens of CRS and FRS.
- This work produced new data for laying hens in different production systems and increased understanding of intestinal microorganisms in hens.

Shi et al., 3 Biotech (2019), doi.org/10.1007/s13205

ENA Metadata Model: Study

STUDY

ENA Metadata Model: Study

EMBL-EBI Services Research Training About us EMBL-EBI

ENA Webin Submissions Portal Support Manage Account Logout

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *

Short descriptive study title *

Study Name

Detailed study abstract *

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations

Study Attributes

Add Study Attributes

ENA Metadata Model: Samples

The researchers took samples from Lohmann hens from CRS and FRS in the same geographical location.

Samples came from caecal content of hens.

Multiple individuals were sampled, and the details of each sample were logged in the database.

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

STUDY

Sample

Age: 120 days
Location: USA
Sample 1

Sample

Age: 120 days
Location: USA
Sample 2

Sample

Age: 120 days
Location: USA
Sample 3

Sample

Age: 120 days
Location: USA
Sample 12

Sample

Age: 120 days
Location: USA
Sample 21

Sample

Age: 120 days
Location: USA
Sample 10

Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

Minimum amount of information expected to describe biological samples required for registration in ENA

Sample Checklists

There is a minimum amount of information required during ENA sample registration and all samples must conform to a defined checklist of expected metadata values. The most suitable checklist for sample registration depends on the type of the sample.

These sample checklists have been developed to meet the needs of different research communities. Different communities have different requirements on the minimum metadata expected to describe biological samples. For any questions regarding checklists, contact us [here](#).

Filter by accession/name/description/field name

Accession	Name	Description
ERC000012	GSC MixS air	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000013	GSC MixS host associated	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000014	GSC MixS human associated	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000015	GSC MixS human gut	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000016	GSC MixS human oral	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000017	GSC MixS human skin	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000018	GSC MixS human vaginal	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.

Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

- ENA metadata checklists guided by standards working groups and the communities
 - Keep up with requirements within communities
- Rich standardised metadata facilitates linking to source information
- General minimum requirements (INSDC)
 - Organism information mandatory and linked with NCBI taxonomy
 - INSDC spatiotemporal policy: mandatory provision of collection date & geographic location
 - INSDC missing value reporting

INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update (03-03-2023)

[Home](#) > [News & Announcements](#) > [INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update \(03-03-2023\)](#)

INSDC continues its aim to increase the number of sequences for which the origin of the sample can be precisely located in time and space through harmonisation of accurate geographical annotation and date and time of collection information.

ENA Sample Checklist Groups

Please select a checklist group first.

Environmental Checklists This group currently includes Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC) MixS sample checklists

Marine Checklists This group currently includes Micro B3 and Tara Oceans sample checklists

Other Checklists This group currently includes the ENA default sample checklist and a few project specific checklists

Pathogens Checklists This group currently includes several prokaryote and virus pathogen sample checklists

[Back](#)

[Next](#)

ENA Metadata Model: Sample – MlxS host associated

You have selected **GSC MlxS host associated**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	tax_id	Text field	None	Taxonomy ID of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Entries in the NCBI Taxonomy database have integer taxon IDs. See our tips for sample taxonomy here
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	scientific_name	Text field	None	Scientific name of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Scientific names typically follow the binomial nomenclature. For example, the scientific name for humans is Homo sapiens.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_alias	Text field	None	Unique name of the sample. If not selected system will auto generate an unique alias
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_title	Text field	None	Title of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_description	Text field	None	Description of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	project name	Text field	None	Name of the project within which the sequencing was organized
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	collection date	Regular expression	None	The date the sample was collected with the intention of sequencing, either as an instance (single point in time) or interval. In case no exact time is available, the date/time can be right truncated i.e. all of these are valid ISO8601 compliant times: 2008-01-23T19:23:10+00:00; 2008-01-23T19:23:10; 2008-01-23; 2008-01; 2008.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (country and/or sea)	Permitted values	None	The geographical origin of where the sample was collected from, with the intention of sequencing, as defined by the country or sea name. Country or sea names should be chosen from the INSDC country list (http://insdc.org/country.html) .
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (latitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by latitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees and in WGS84 system
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (longitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by longitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees and in WGS84 system
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	broad scale environmental context	Text field	None	Report the major environmental system the sample or specimen came from. The system(s) identified should have a coarse spatial grain, to provide the general environmental context of where the sampling was done (e.g. in the forest or a rainforest). We recommend using subclasses of EcoSys biome class : https://...

ENA Metadata Model: Sample – MixS host associated

Mandatory Fields				
Recommended Fields				
Optional Fields				
Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	trophic level	Permitted values	None	Trophic levels are the feeding position in a food chain. Microbes can be a range of producers (e.g. chemolithotroph)
<input type="checkbox"/>	observed biotic relationship	Permitted values	None	Description of relationship(s) between the subject organism and other organism(s) it is associated with. E.g., parasite on species X, mutualist with species Y. The target organism is the subject of the relationship, and the other organism(s) is the object.
<input type="checkbox"/>	known pathogenicity	Text field	None	To what is the entity pathogenic, for instance plant, fungi, bacteria
<input type="checkbox"/>	relationship to oxygen	Permitted values	None	Is this organism an aerobe, anaerobe? Please note that aerobic and anaerobic are valid descriptors for microbial environments
<input type="checkbox"/>	propagation	Text field	None	The type of reproduction from the parent stock. Values for this field is specific to different taxa. For phage or virus: lytic/lysogenic/temperate/obligately lytic. For plasmids: incompatibility group. For eukaryotes: sexual/asexual. Mandatory for MIGs of eukaryotes, plasmids and viruses.
<input type="checkbox"/>	observed host symbionts		None	The taxonomic name of the organism(s) found living in mutualistic, commensalistic, or parasitic symbiosis with the specific host.
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection device	Text field	None	The device used to collect an environmental sample. It is recommended to use terms listed under environmental sampling device (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO) and/or terms listed under specimen collection device (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/GENEPIO_0002094).
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection method	Text field	None	The method employed for collecting the sample. Can be provided in the form of a PMID, DOI, url or text.
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample storage temperature	Regular expression	°C	temperature at which sample was stored, e.g. -80
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample storage location	Text field	None	Location at which sample was stored, usually name of a specific freezer/room. Indicate the location name.
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample disease stage	Text field	None	stage of the disease at the time of sample collection, e.g. inoculation, penetration,

The Metadata Model: Sample - Taxonomy

Taxon: 256318
metagenome [species]

Lineage
unclassified sequences, metagenomes

Tax Tree

Abbreviated lineage

- > unclassified sequences
- > metagenomes
- > ecological metagenomes
 - activated carbon metagenome [species]
 - activated sludge metagenome [species]
 - aerosol metagenome [species]
 - air metagenome [species]
 - alkal sediment metagenome [species]
 - anaerobic digester metagenome [species]
 - archaeline metagenome [species]
 - ant fungus garden metagenome [species]
 - aquaculture metagenome [species]
 - aquatic metagenome [species]
 - aquifer metagenome [species]
 - ballast water metagenome [species]
 - beach sand metagenome [species]

Taxon: 256318
metagenome [species]

Lineage
unclassified sequences, metagenomes

Tax Tree

Abbreviated lineage

- > unclassified sequences
- > metagenomes
 - > ecological metagenomes
 - metagenome [species]
 - > organismal metagenomes
 - algae metagenome [species]
 - amphibian metagenome [species]
 - annelid metagenome [species]
 - ant metagenome [species]
 - aquatic viral metagenome [species]
 - bat metagenome [species]
 - beetle metagenome [species]
 - bird metagenome [species]
 - blood metagenome [species]
 - bovine gut metagenome [species]
 - bovine metagenome [species]

- The taxon ID is an essential attribute of your ENA samples
- Make sure you use environmental taxonomy

chicken gut metagenome

Taxonomy ID: 506600

Scientific name: **chicken gut metagenome**

Inherited blast name: **metagenomes**

Rank: **species**

Gallus gallus

Taxonomy ID: 9031

Scientific name: **Gallus gallus**

Inherited blast name: **birds**

Rank: **species**

ENA Metadata Model: Experiments

After amplification and purification, sequencing was performed on an Illumina MiSeq System

ENA Metadata Model: Experiments

ENA Metadata Model: Runs

The result of these 6 paired end experiments is 12 FASTQ files.

These are compressed and uploaded to a database, where they undergo processing and wait to be made public.

```
@SRR2960126.1 1/1
GCCAGCTATATCAGTTTCCTTTGTGATGGGGCGTTTATGTAAGGGATGGGTATGGAACGCACCCTGGCTAGAACGAAAAGACTTGCTAT
TGTGAAGTTA
+
=;?AD=D?FDB???ACGHGGEHCEEHC@GDG>GDGHFF@9?C<38BFEACHIID>EEC>A3@D;?=:ABCA?
@@A8=B=B>89>ACCCACCADC3@4@@A
@SRR2960126.2 2/1
GTGGGTAACATTTGGAACAGAAAAACAAAAGTAGAATGGTGGGTGAGGAGAACAATAAAAAATGATACTTCATTTAATTATCATTTAGA
GATGTATATC
+
CCCFDFDFHHHHHIIJIIJJJJJJJJJJII?
DGIJJJJBFIFFGGIJJIIJJJJHHHHHFFFFFFFDEEEEDFEDEEEDEEEEDDDDDDEEFFDD
@SRR2960126.3 3/1
CTTTTAAACAAAGATTTTTTAAAAAATGCTGTGCTGTAATCTACTAGCAAAAACCTAATTTGCTAGTTGCATTGGAAGATATTGATACT
TGACAATTTA
+
CCFFFFFHDFGHHHJIIJJIIJJJJIIJIGHIIJJJJIIJJJJJJJJIGJIHGHHHHFFFFFFFEDCCADCDEEEDDD
DDDDDDDDDD
@SRR2960126.4 4/1
GCTTTTTTTCGGCAACGATGGAATCGATCAATTGTTATTGTGACAGCTAAATTGATAAAACAAAATGATACAGTTTCAAACCTGATCAAAA
ATTTGCAGCA
+
@=?DDDBDFBHD<FBHAHBD@FGIEDHGH?7BB9BFGHIDF@====FCGEGGGH3AEHC;@@DDF@C>;A@AC:
5-5;>@C@CCC::@ACBA@C:4>:(2
```

ENA Metadata Model: Runs

ENA Metadata Model: Runs

You have selected **Fastq File Type**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Show Description

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Field Label	Permitted Value	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample	Sample		Sample alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	study	Study		Study alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	instrument_model	Instrument model	Permitted values ▾	The sequencing instrument model used in the experiment
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_name	Library name		The name for the library if any.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_source	Library source	Permitted values ▾	The type of source material that is being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_selection	Library selection	Permitted values ▾	The method used to select for or against, enrich, or screen the material being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_strategy	Library strategy	Permitted values ▾	The sequencing technique intended for this library.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_layout	Library layout	Permitted values ▾	The library layout specifies whether to expect single or paired configuration of reads.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_name	Forward file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_md5	Forward File checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_name	Reverse file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_md5	Reverse file checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Project: PRJEB53667

Characterization by shotgun sequencing of the caecal metagenome of broilers raised in a farm in the American Midwest. Data was generated by DSM Nutritional Products.

Secondary Study Accession: ERP138479

Study Title: Characterization by shotgun sequencing of the caecal metagenome of broilers raised in a farm in the American Midwest.

Center Name: Institut National pour la Recherche Agronomique (FRANCE):INRA-META

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-10-27

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2023-02-17

Project description and metadata

General

View: XML
XML (STUDY)

Download: XML
XML (STUDY)

Cross References: Show

ORCID Data Claims: Show

Related ENA Records: Show

Navigate around the object

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Data

Read Files: Hide

Wgs Files: Show

Navigate on data

Download report: JSON TSV Get download script Download selected files

[Download All](#)

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP
PRJEB53667	SAMEA111509225	ERX9949348	ERR10422953	506600	chicken gut metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR10422953_1.fastq.gz <input type="checkbox"/> ERR10422953_2.fastq.gz
PRJEB53667	SAMEA111509226	ERX9949349	ERR10422954	506600	chicken gut metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR10422954_1.fastq.gz <input type="checkbox"/> ERR10422954_2.fastq.gz
PRJEB53667	SAMEA111509227	ERX9949350	ERR10422955	506600	chicken gut metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR10422955_1.fastq.gz <input type="checkbox"/> ERR10422955_2.fastq.gz

Run-centric data table

Information for a single run

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

ENA Metadata Model: Navigation Bar

- View project metadata
- Show/hide different information about project
- Explore cross-references related to project
- Explore reads/analyses files

General

View:	XML
	XML (STUDY)
Download:	XML
	XML (STUDY)
Cross References:	Show
ORCID Data Claims:	Show
Related ENA Records:	Show

Data

Read Files:	Show
Wgs Files:	Show

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Secondary Study Accession: ERP138479

Study Title: Characterization by shotgun sequencing of the caecal metagenome of broilers raised in a farm in the American Midwest.

Center Name: Institut National pour la Recherche Agronomique (FRANCE);INRA-META

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-10-27

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2023-02-17

Related ENA Records

Result	Count
Experiment	48
Assembly	219
Genome assembly contig set	219
Run	48

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Experiment: ERX9949348

Illumina HiSeq 2000 paired end sequencing; Illumina HiSeq 2000 paired-end sequencing

Organism: [chicken gut metagenome](#)
Experiment Accession: ERX9949348
Instrument Platform: ILLUMINA
Instrument Model: Illumina HiSeq 2000
Center Name: Institut National pour la Recherche Agronomique (FRANCE);INRA-META
Library Layout: PAIRED
Library Strategy: WGS
Library Source: METAGENOMIC
Library Selection: RANDOM
Run Accession: ERR10422953

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: JSON TSV

Get download script

Download selected files

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP
PRJEB53667	SAMEA111509225	ERX9949348	ERR10422953	506600	chicken gut metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR10422953_1.fastq.gz <input type="checkbox"/> ERR10422953_2.fastq.gz

General

View: XML
Download: XML
Cross References: Show
ORCID Data Claims: Show

Data

Read Files: Hide

Tags

environment by geolocation
terrestrial
freshwater

New tags feature

Annotations of ENA objects

Controlled textual annotations provided to metadata objects to facilitate search and filtering

Data Submission at ENA

Data Submission at ENA

- There are three submissions routes
- *'Interactive Submission'*:
 - Use your browser to fill out web forms describing your work
- *'Programmatic Submission'*:
 - Describe your work in XML documents, submit them to us using cURL
- *'Webin-CLI'*:
 - Smart submission interface, made in-house

Data Submission: Interactive

- Register your objects using your browser
- Familiar and largely accessible
- Prepare spreadsheets for bigger submissions

The screenshot displays the ENA Webin Submissions Portal interface. The top navigation bar includes the ENA logo, 'Webin Submissions Portal', and links for 'Support', 'Manage Account', and 'Logout (Webin-60876)'. The main content area is titled 'Register study (project)' and contains a 'Submission Details' section. This section includes a 'Release date' field with the value '22-05-2024', a 'Study Name' field with the value 'Arabidopsis mutation accumulation', and a checkbox for 'Will you provide functional genome annotation?'. A 'Short descriptive study title' field contains the text 'Testing de novo mutation calling artefacts by re-sequencing single mutation accumulation'. Below this is a 'Detailed study abstract' field with a scrollable text area containing a paragraph about mutation bias results. At the bottom, there is a 'PubMed Citations Registration' section with a table of citations.

PubMedId	Title	Remove
9784120	Arabidopsis thaliana: a model plant for genome analysis.	

Data Submission: Programmatic

- Prepare an XML/JSON file describing your submission
- Send this to us via HTTPS
- Correct format for JSON/XML files important for successful submission and validation of data.

- Example cURL command:

```
curl -u username:password \  
-F "SAMPLE=@sample.xml" \  
-F "SUBMISSION=@submission.xml" \  
"https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit/"
```

```
<SUBMISSION>  
  <ACTIONS>  
    <ACTION>  
      <ADD/>  
    </ACTION>  
  </ACTIONS>  
</SUBMISSION>
```

```
<SAMPLE alias="ME5176V2" context_name="">  
  <TITLE>human gastric microbiota, mucosal</TITLE>  
  <SAMPLE_NAME>  
    <TAXON_ID>1284369</TAXON_ID>  
    <SCIENTIFIC_NAME>stomach metagenome</SCIENTIFIC_NAME>  
    <COMMON_NAME></COMMON_NAME>  
  </SAMPLE_NAME>  
  <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>collection date</TAG>  
      <VALUE>2010</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>host body site</TAG>  
      <VALUE>mucosa of stomach</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>human-associated environmental package</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human-associated</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (latitude)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>1.81</VALUE>  
      <UNITS>DD</UNITS>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (longitude)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>-78.76</VALUE>  
      <UNITS>DD</UNITS>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (country and/or sea)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Colombia</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (region and locality)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Tumaco</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environment (biome)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>coast</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>project name</TAG>  
      <VALUE>test12V2</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environment (feature)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human-associated habitat</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environmental medium</TAG>  
      <VALUE>gastric fluid</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>broad-scale environmental context</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human gut</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>local environmental context</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human gut</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>ENA-CHECKLIST</TAG>  
      <VALUE>ERC000015</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
  </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>  
</SAMPLE>
```


ENA - Submission Tools & Data Portals

Webin-CLI Data Submission

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Webin Portal

Welcome to the Webin Submissions Portal

You can use this service for a range of submission activities as well as reports on your submissions. For help with submitting your data, including the use of this interface, please refer to our Help Guides. Please familiarise yourself with the different options available. New users are advised to take a moment to understand the interface.

•Studies tab

- Used for registering studies and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered studies

•Samples tab

- Used to register new samples, requesting taxonomy for novel/unidentified/published species and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered samples

•Raw reads/experiments tab

- Used to register runs/experiments and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered runs/experiments
- Can also be used to track run files validation/processing

Studies (Projects)

Studies Report

Register Samples

Register Novel Taxonomy

Submit XMLs (advanced)

Raw Reads (Experiments and Runs)

Runs Report

Run Files Report

Run Processing Report

Unsubmitted Files Report

Submit XMLs (advanced)

Samples

Samples Report

Data Analyses

Assemblies and annotated sequences must be submitted with Webin-CLI. Other analyses can be submitted as XMLs.

Generate Annotated Sequence Spreadsheet

Submit XMLs (advanced)

Analyses Report

Analysis File Report

Analysis Processing Report

•ENA Metadata Model showing data objects and data structure

•Analyses tab

- Used to download annotated sequences template spreadsheet and view submitted analyses metadata.
- Can also be used to track analyses files processing.

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Webin Account

- Each submission requires a Webin account.
- Can be created by submitting web form on the Webin Portal page.
- Requires fields such as centre name, country and user credentials.
- Fields such as centre name, contact information can be updated.
- Metagenomics consent box to allow MGnify to access and analyse metagenomic data.

Account Details

Abbreviated center name	Password
Full center name	Confirm Password
Laboratory Name	
Address	
Country	

Contact Information

Add At Least One Contact

No Sensitive Data

I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.

Metagenomics Consent

By keeping this box checked you give consent to the EBI MGnify team to analyse those data for which you have requested a pre-publication confidential hold. Note that the data as well as the analysis results will remain confidential until the specified release date of the associated sequencing study. If you are also requesting assembly of your data by MGnify, you also give consent to MGnify to submit these assemblies to your ENA study on your behalf. MGnify will not change any metadata or data you have already submitted but may need to perform updates to submissions performed by their team in exceptional circumstances. This service provides pre-publication state-of-the-art analysis results, along with visualisations, that you may use in subsequent publications. The service is described in <http://europepmc.org/article/MED/31696235> and we kindly request, should you use these analyses in your publications, that you cite this paper.

I give consent and confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable

Save Cancel

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Study

- Study required for each submission at the ENA.
- Needs to be registered interactively or programmatically. Webin-CLI does not support study registration.
- Groups data objects under one project.
- Authority on release date of data objects linked to a study.
- Add publications and study attributes to study metadata.

Webin-CLI does not support study registration

The screenshot shows a web form for submitting study details. It is divided into several sections: 'Submission Details' with fields for 'Release date', 'Study Name', and a checkbox for 'Will you provide functional genome annotation?'; 'Short descriptive study title' and 'Detailed study abstract' text areas; 'PubMed Citations Registration' with an 'Add PubMed Citations' button; and 'Study Attributes' with an 'Add Study Attributes' button. At the bottom right, there are 'Submit' and 'Cancel' buttons.

```
<PROJECT_SET>
  <PROJECT alias="cheddar_cheese">
    <NAME>WGS Streptomyces iranensis</NAME>
    <TITLE>Characterisation of Microbial Diversity and...</TITLE>
    <DESCRIPTION>This study aimed to characterise the interaction of microbial...</DESCRIPTION>
    <SUBMISSION_PROJECT>
      <SEQUENCING_PROJECT/>
    </SUBMISSION_PROJECT>
  </PROJECT>
</PROJECT_SET>
```

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Sample

- Samples can now be registered with Webin-CLI (in JSON file format)
- Interactive and programmatic sample submission more widely used with reads.
- Range of sample checklists to choose from including Environmental, Pathogen, Plant and Marine checklists.
- Include required, recommended and mandatory metadata fields.
- Mandatory minimum metadata fields for all checklists include taxonomy information, sample details, collection dates and geographic location.

```
{
  "samples": [
    {
      "alias": "uniqueAlias",
      "title": "human gut microbiota, mucosal",
      "organism": {
        "taxonId": "408170"
      },
      "attributes": [
        {
          "tag": "project name",
          "value": "human gut study"
        },
        {
          "tag": "collection date",
          "value": "2010-01-20"
        },
        {
          "tag": "host body site",
          "value": "Mucosa of stomach"
        },
        {
          "tag": "human-associated environmental package",
          "value": "human-associated"
        },
        {
          "tag": "geographic location (latitude)",
          "value": "1.81",
          "unit": "DD"
        },
        {
          "tag": "geographic location (longitude)",
          "value": "-78.76",
          "unit": "DD"
        },
        {
          "tag": "geographic location (country and/or sea)",
          "value": "Colombia"
        },
        {
          "tag": "geographic location (region and locality)",
          "value": "Tumaco"
        },
        {
          "tag": "environment (biome)",
          "value": "Coast"
        },
        {
          "tag": "environment (feature)",
          "value": "human-associated habitat"
        },
        {
          "tag": "environmental medium",
          "value": "gastric fluid"
        },
        {
          "tag": "broad-scale environmental context",
          "value": "human gut"
        },
        {
          "tag": "local environmental context",
          "value": "human gut"
        },
        {
          "tag": "ena-checklist",
          "value": "ENC000013"
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

```
{
  "study": "PRJEB12345",
  "sample": {
    {
      "alias": "sediment_sample",
      "title": "Sample derived from sediment in Antarctica",
      "organism": {
        "taxonId": "77133"
      },
      "attributes": [
        {
          "tag": "collection date",
          "value": "2025-01-30"
        },
        {
          "tag": "geographic location (country and/or sea)",
          "value": "Antarctica"
        },
        . . .
      ]
    },
    "name": "ena-EXPERIMENT-TEST-28-10-2024-01-02:26:880-109",
    "platform": "ILLUMINA",
    "instrument": "Illumina MiSeq",
    "insert_size": "390",
    "libraryName": "unspecified",
    "library-source": "GENOMIC",
    "library_selection": "PCR",
    "libraryStrategy": "AMPLICON",
    "fastq": {
      "value": "test_single_run_2.fastq.gz",
      "attributes": {
        "read_type": ["single"]
      }
    }
  }
}
```

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Checklist	ERC000013	GSC MixS host associated							
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	sample derived from	collection date	geographic location (country and/or sea)	geographic location (latitude)	geographic location (longitude) br
3	#units							DD		DD
4										
5										

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Run

- Raw read sequencing data object, final step for submission of raw reads.
- Submit reads using a manifest file in plain text or JSON format.
- Only BAM, CRAM and Fastq file formats for raw read data supported by Webin-CLI.
- Validates files before submission.
- Successful submission returns a run accession with the sequence files metadata and an experiment accession with the library metadata.

manifest.txt

```
STUDY ERP013289
SAMPLE ERS980556
NAME ena-EXPERIMENT-TEST-13-03-2025-01:02:26:880-109
INSTRUMENT Illumina MiSeq
INSERT_SIZE 390
LIBRARY_SOURCE GENOMIC
LIBRARY_SELECTION PCR
LIBRARY_STRATEGY AMPLICON
FASTQ test_single_run.fastq.gz
```

manifest.json

```
{
  "study": "ERP013289",
  "sample": "ERS980556",
  "name": "ena-EXPERIMENT-TEST-28-10-2024-01:02:26:880-109",
  "platform": "ILLUMINA",
  "instrument": "Illumina MiSeq",
  "insert_size": "390",
  "libraryName": "unspecified",
  "library-source": "GENOMIC",
  "library_selection": "PCR",
  "libraryStrategy": "AMPLICON",
  "fastq": {
    "value": "test_single_run.fastq.gz",
    "attributes": {
      "read_type": ["single"]
    }
  }
}
```

Webin-CLI Data Submission

Summary

<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>

- The ENA provides **scientific record** of sequencing data.
- Established in the early 1980s, extended for **new technologies and applications**.
- Comprehensive record of world's **nucleotide sequencing information** covering raw read data, sequence assembly information and functional annotation.
- Presents large amounts of a diverse range of data in a consistent manner, making use of **data and metadata Models**.
- Metadata model requires minimal mandatory metadata in line with **FAIR data principles**.
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**.
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training.
- **Data submission** routes: Interactive, programmatic and Webin-CLI.
- Webin-CLI Submission using **manifest files** submitted with the command line.
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals.

Handy links

- ENA Browser: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>
- ENA Submission/Retrieval Guide: <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/general-guide.html>
- ENA Helpdesk: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/support>
- Advanced Search: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/advanced-search>
- Webin Portal: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>
- Webin TEST Portal: <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

**Thank you
Any Questions?**

Webin-CLI Data Submission Practical

During this exercise, you will implement some of the skills you have just learnt and submit some raw read sequencing data to the ENA.

1. Register a study interactively using web form
2. Register your sample interactively using spreadsheet
3. Submit runs with Webin-CLI using command line

Thank you
Any Questions?

